

Estimation of One Way Delay without Clock Synchronization in Mobile Adhoc Network

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Abstract – One way network delay is a critical parameter in real time applications as it allows the application to assess the perceived quality. However, it is very difficult to estimate one way delay of the packets traversing the network. The reason behind it is that the internet architecture is based on the end-to-end principle. The endpoints are connected to the network independently, without clock synchronization. The need for one-way delay estimation/measurement in the Internet is in order to grasp the exact the exact state of the Internet. There are several one-way delay measurement methods which uses a synchronized clock between the endpoints. Therefore in this paper, we propose a one-way delay estimation method which does not need the clock synchronization between the endpoints. This method observes the incoming packets and then makes the measurements without using a synchronized clock and this making it independent of the network environment. The proposed non-synchronized one-way delay estimation has the ability to measure one way network delay and obtain the full spectrum of the delays of the real time protocol session.

Keywords: One-way Delay estimation, Clock Synchronization, Round Trip Time, MANET

I. Introduction

One-way delay is a critical parameter in real time systems like VoIP, since it determines the call quality. It is well known that measuring one-way delay of the RTP packet is difficult because it requires clock synchronization. A common approach is to have a synchronized clock between the sender and receiver which can be achieved by using GPS, CDMA or NTP [13]. RTP packets may be time stamped both on the sender and receiver, thereby allowing accurate measurements to be made [5]. The required clock synchronization is a drawback of the conventional one-way delay measurement. In most cases, the synchronized clock is not available because the endpoints are connected to the network independently.

There are several one-way delay measurement tools available. However, they rely on having an implementation of a synchronized clock between the endpoints, by using GPS, CDMA or NTP. Examples include One-Way Active Measurement Protocol (OWAMP) [12] and PingER (Ping End-to-End Reporting). These tools provide active measurement to study the network delay and performance. Active measurement works by injecting the probe packets to the network. The packets are time-stamped both on the sender and receiver, which allows accurate measurements to be made. However, the active measurement cannot truly reflect the real performance because it is the measurement of the probe packets, not the RP packets that actually carry voice data. Passive measurement aims

to measure the delay of the RTP packets themselves [10]. So the measurements can be more accurate to assess the quality of RTP packets. In addition, passive measurement does not introduce additional traffic to the network that could affect the packets. However, passive measurement has the limitation in that it cannot modify the standard of RTP packets to add the time-stamp to facilitate the measurement of one-way delay.

Added with the constraint of the synchronized clock, passive measurement of one-way delay of the RTP packet becomes a real challenge. UDP measures the delay imposed on packets being sent to the other end of the connection. This measurement only includes buffering delay along the link, not propagation delay nor the routing delay. It does this by always comparing all measurements to a baseline measurement, to cancel out any fixed delay. By focusing on the variable delay along a link, it will specifically detect points where there might be congestion, since those points will have buffers. Delay on the return link is explicitly not included in the delay measurement. This is because in a peer-to-peer application, the other end is likely to be connected via a modem with same output buffer restrictions as we assume for the sending side. The other end having its output queue full is not an indication of congestion on the path going the other way.

In order to measure on-way delay for packets, we cannot rely on clocks being synchronized, especially not at the microsecond level. Instead, the actual time it takes for a packet to arrive at the destination is not measured, only the change in the transit time is measured.

II. Related Works

Nowadays the evaluation of performance measurement in computer networks is an important issue. To ensure the quality of service of the network communication, one of the most important network performance parameters is the one-way-delay (OWD). For accurate OWD estimation, it is essential to consider some parameters that can influence the measure, such as the operating system and in particular, the threads, which are concurrent with the measurement application. Moreover, OWD estimation is not an easy task, because it can be affected by synchronization uncertainties. This section aims to review the different solutions proposed in the scientific literature for OWD measurement.

The accuracy of measurement of OWD is based on a relative synchronization and therefore an absolute synchronization to UTC is not required. Difference synchronization techniques are used. The most accurate one is to provide each site of measurement with a precise external clock. An atomic clock or a GPS receiver is used but this solution suffers from bad scalability. The cost of atomic clock is very high and installation of a GPS antenna may be difficult in some localities.

In [13], an experimental comparison of different NTP synchronization strategies to measure OWD in large area networks is presented. The NTP presents the direct method of one-way delay measurement using clock synchronization. The measurement sites are synchronized using NTP servers. No other source of exact time is needed for this type of measurement methods. It uses a PPS(Pulse Per Second) signal from GPS.

Jeong et al proposes an architecture of measurement system which measures IETF's IP performance metrics (IPPM) such as one-delay, one-way packet loss and packet delay variation in the Internet. It uses a GPS to synchronize the measurement systems and thereby provides the precision up to micro-second. To improve the accuracy of one-way delay measurement, the proposed system employs timestamps at the Ethernet frame level.

Precise time synchronization is essential for one-way delay measurement. There are three possible ways to adjust local clock. First, a standalone precise clock such as atomic clock is installed in each location. The result is precisely synchronized, but with high cost. Second, each clock is adjusted using PPS signal from a GPS receiver. Finally, all clocks is synchronized over a network using NTP protocol. Available estimates of achievable precision using NTP protocol range from 1 to 5 msec. Therefore, this decide to use a GPS receiver in the first generation of the tool. There are certain issues which must be considered in practical use of GPS receivers for time synchronization [11].

When implementing networks with QoS guarantees, precise measurement of all network QoS characteristics is necessary. This is needed to observe the behavior of various traffic handling mechanisms on different patterns of data, for example, to see influence of handling a traffic aggregate on a micro flow behavior, which is the case in different server networks and to check if the agreed Service Level Specification (SLS) is adhered by bot the user and the network.

III. Proposed System

The network delay consists of four components: Transmission delay, router processing delay, Queuing delay and propagation delay. The router processing delay is normally insignificant because it is very small relative to the other delays. So router processing delay can be negligible in the calculation. Transmission delay is the time required to put all the bits in the packet for transmission. It is equal to the packet size divided by the transmission link capacity. In a high speed network, transmission delay can be very small and negligible. Transmission delay on a limited bandwidth access link may be relatively large. But, because the access link is usually close or directly connected to the endpoints, the link capacity is often known by the sender. Thus, transmission delay can be estimated.

Queuing delay is the time that packet waits in a buffer to be transmitted. It depends on several factors including the egress link capacity, the size of the buffer, the router scheduling policy and the amount of congestion. The propagation delay is the time it takes for the packet to travel along the physical path. It is equal to the path distance between the sender and receiver divided by the speed of the electronic signal. Depending on the type of medium, the electronic signal typically travels at 2/3 of the speed of light. Since the endpoints normally do not know the distance, propagation delay cannot be calculated. In a synchronized system, it can be obtained by using the timestamps when the packet leaves the sender and arrives at the receiver. Such a measurement includes all the four delay components.

We propose a RTP measurement methodology that can contribute significantly to overcome the challenge of measuring the one-way delay of RTP packets. The proposed algorithm is running on the receiver that monitors the arriving RTP packets, using the information provided in the standard RTP packet. The proposed algorithm can build the transmission timing of the sender that is virtually synchronized with the reception timing.

The transmission and reception timing are synchronized virtually by unknown offset that includes propagation, transmission and router processing delay. Since the router processing delay is negligible, the unknown offset is reduced to the sum of propagation and transmission delays. The mechanism requires that the sender logs the time when the packet is transmitted.

Upon receiving the packet, the receiver is required to return an acknowledgement immediately to the sender. The acknowledgement can be as simple as a UDP packet. The sender then logs the time when receiving the acknowledgement packet. The observed round-trip time can be broken down into the delay components as follows

$$RTT = TD_p + PD_p + QD_p + TD_a + PD_a + QD_a$$

Queuing delay (QD) is the key component of the one-way network delay whereas the other delay components such as transmission delay (TD) and propagation delay (PD) are fixed, queuing delay is very critical because it is highly variable and unpredictable. Being able to measure the queuing delay enables the proposed algorithm to estimate the one-way network delay at a very high level of accuracy.

More specifically, the sender can transmit the RTP packets exactly at the packetization period which means the inter-departure gap. It keep track of the ongoing epoch at the exact same packetization period. However the clock is not perfect, Time skew happens at both the sender and the receiver. The dispersion gap describes the interval in which the arriving packet is dispersed from its inter departure gap and is defined as

$$\text{Dispersion gap} = \text{packetization delay} + \text{Queuing delay}$$

The difference between the arrival time and the transmission time is the queuing delay. The first arriving packet experiences zero queuing delay. The proposed algorithm calculates the packetization delay from the payload size of the incoming RTP packets which is then used to construct the transmission timing on the receiver

IV. Simulation Setup

We use NS-2 simulator to form mobile adhoc network and the configuration setup is shown in the Table 1.

Simulator Variables	Value
Channel	Wireless Channel
Propagation model	Two Ray ground
Mac Protocol	802.11
Antenna	Omni Antenna
Queue length	50
Number of mobile nodes	50
Routing Protocol	AODV
Area	800m x 800m

V. Conclusion

In this paper, we propose one-way delay estimation without clock synchronization that measure one-way

network delay and obtain the full spectrum of the delays of the RTP session. The proposed work is unique in it and can be adapted by other systems. The knowledge about optimizing the packetization can be applied in any system. The VoIP agent including routers and gateways can use the one-way delay estimation in order to choose alternate route, estimating the bandwidth required for transmission, predicting the loss of packets etc. This can also be used as the input for perceptual speech quality assessment algorithms.

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